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RECENT REFERENCES IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION RESEARCH

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Topics: another topic relevant to the conference but not listed above

Keywords: engineering education research

Rationale

Although engineering education research (EER) has been evolving and expanding significantly in recent years, it is still a relatively new field in the European context. As a result, those with an interest in EER and particularly those entering the field, frequently report challenges in gaining an overall sense of existing EER scholarship. The workshop aims to broaden participants' knowledge of important publications within the field by analyzing and discussing a small number of recent publications selected by the SEFI Working Group on Engineering Education Research as being recent, high quality work, in the field.

Participant engagement

The very successful workshop format of the SEFI 2018 workshop will be repeated.

After a short introduction and mingling exercise, heterogeneous groups will be composed that allow for small group discussions. In addition to analyzing specific publications, participants will have opportunities to discuss with Working Group members the selection of these particular publications as key works.

Takeaway

The attendees will have gained insight in recent European Engineering Education publications as they will receive a list of recent recommended publications from the field. Participant conclusions will be made available online after the session, on the website of the working group.